

Conference Abstract

Investigating the Impact of Green R&D, Transformational Leadership, and Cross-Cultural Approaches on Performance Management in the Manufacturing Sector

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Abstract

In the present era, environmental sustainability is a transformative concept that is rapidly penetrating all facets of our lives and professional environments. Belgium focuses on environmental sustainability offers a wide range of green initiatives to sustain its environmental performance. However, the previous research has failed to determine the extent to which Green R & D Investment, Green Transformational Leadership, Green Cross Culture perspective impact the Belgium manufacturing organizations. The main rationale for performing this research was to determine the above green initiative's impact on the Belgium manufacturing organization. For this, a mixed-method approach has been utilized. Data from 254 respondents have been collected. This data was further analyzed through the analyzed the SPSS to perform the quantitative analysis. The results of the quantitative analysis show the Green R & D Investment. Green Transformational Leadership significantly influence green performance management (GPM) since its significance value is less than 0.5. At the same time, the Green Cross Culture Perspective does not pose any impact on GPM since it has a p-value of 0.48. On the other hand, qualitative data was gathered through the focus group interviews. Nine managers have been included in to focus group interview. In the focus group interview, managers depict

the all the considered initiatives are vital for their green sustainability. However, green cross-cultural perceptive strategies should be enhanced more and consider both collectivism, and individualism elements for green sustainability. In spite of positive research results, this research also implies that the manufacturing organization in Belgium need to continuously change R&D investment strategies, focus on leader tanning, and increase employee engagement to ensure the successful implementation of green performance management.

Keywords

Performance Management, Transformational Leader, R&D Investment, Cross Culture

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.